

***Solvate Suite* Part I: A Complete and Modular Command-Line User Interface for Tool Integration in Molecular Simulation Studies of Liquid Systems**

Additional Examples

Program Dependencies

Simulation Box Creation

- PackMol v20.14.2
- Q-Force v0.6.12

Electronic Structure and Molecular Dynamics Simulation Programs

- xTB v6.6.1
- CREST v2.12
- ORCA 5.0
- GROMACS 2023.3

Visualization Programs

- JMol
- VMD

Scripts Interpreter

- Python 3.10

General Features

Program Interface and Job Execution Sequence

The program was developed with the aim of offering users an organized, intuitive, and standardized interface for interaction. The initial interaction involves executing either the “solvate” or “solvate -s1” command. This action will prompt the following screen to appear:

a `solvate <solute> <solvent> [<-options>]`

b `<solute> = File with solute geometry (.com/log/inp/out/xyz/xtb)`
`<solvent> = File with solvent geometry (.com/log/inp/out/xyz/xtb)`

c *STEP 1: Packing [[PACKS+QMDFF]] [-s1] «PackMol»«qForce»

d Nmol = Number of solvent molecules in the packing step. [Default: 0] [=Determine] [-nm]
dCel = Dimensions of the simulation cell (in nanometers). [Default: Not defined] [-dc]
bCon = Molal concentration of the simulation cell (in mol·kg⁻¹). [Default: Not defined] [-bc]
Prop = Proportion between solvent molecules. [Nsvt1:Nsvt2:...]. [Default: Not defined] [-pr]
Dens = Density of the simulation cell (in g·mL⁻¹). [Default: 1.0] [-ds] (*)
cIon = File with counterion to be added for charge neutrality. [Default: None] [-ci]
Shape = Packaging format (sphere|cube|box). [Default: Sphere/Cube] [-sp]

e *STEP 2: Simulation [[MDRUN]] [-s2]

*STEP 3: Analysis [[DATAS+STATS+PLOTS+TRAJS]] [-s3]

*STEP 4: Clusterization [[HBOND/MICRO]] [-s4]

*STEP 5: Optimization [[GCALC]] [-s5]

*STEP 6: File Management [[FILES]] [-s6]

f (*) Configurable options in automated mode.

The highlighted areas represent: (a) the standard usage of the program; (b) the input files and their formats; (c) the stage of program use, involved modules, and interfaced programs; (d) options, functionality descriptions, default values, and alternate command forms; (e) additional stages, modules, and programs; (f) specific information for each highlighted stage. The first three stages are focused on integration with molecular dynamics programs, and last three focus on integrating electronic structure programs and file management, as detailed below.

COMMAND@LINE:~\$ solvate -s1

solvate <solute> { <solvent>} [<-options>]

<solute> = File with solute geometry (.com/log/inp/out/xyz/xtb)

<solvent> = File with solvent geometry (.com/log/inp/out/xyz/xtb)

 *STEP 1: Packing [[PACKS+QMDF]][-s1] «PackMol»«qForce»

PCauto : Execute the packing procedure with automatic settings. [-pa]
 » Description
 ORC: [Default:250 solvent molecules in spheric shape]
 GMX: [Default: 2000 solvent molecules in cubic shape]
 + -----
 Nmol = Number of solvent molecules in the packing step. [Default: 0] [=Determine] [-nm]
 Npck = Number of packing layers. [Default: 2] [-np]
 dCel = Dimensions of the simulation cell (in nanometers). [Default: Not defined] [-dc]
 gCel = Gap between solute and cell edges (in nanometers). [Default: Not defined] [-dg]
 bCon = Molal concentration of the simulation cell (in mol·kg⁻¹). [Default: Not defined] [-bc]
 cCon = Molar concentration of the simulation cell (in mol·L⁻¹). [Default: Not defined] [-cc]
 Prop = Proportion between solvent molecules. [Nsvt1:Nsvt2:...]. [Default: Not defined] [-pr]
 Dens = Density of the simulation cell (in g·mL⁻¹). [Default: 1.0] [-ds] (*)
 cIon = File with counterion to be added for charge neutrality. [Default: None] [-ci]
 Shape = Packaging format (sphere|cube|box). [Default: Sphere/Cube] [-sp]
 Format = Type of generated file (com|inp|xyz|pdb). [Default: All] [-ft]
 Repack : Resubmit the packing procedure with new parameters. [Default: No] [-rp]
 Force : Execute in forced mode (no warning messages). [Default: No] [-fp]
 Normal : Run in normal mode (normal packing configuration). [Default: No] [-cv]
 Iterat : Run in iterative mode (to adjust tolerance). [Default: No] [-it]
 Backup : Save original input files. [Default: No] [-bk]
 Check : Checks the consistency of simulation box settings. [Default: No] [-ck]

 *STEP 2: Simulation [[MDRUN]][-s2]

*STEP 3: Analysis [[DATAS+STATS+PLOTS+TRAJS]][-s3]

*STEP 4: Clusterization [[HBOND/MICRO]][-s4]

*STEP 5: Optimization [[GALC]][-s5]

*STEP 6: File Management [[FILES]][-s6]

(*) Configurable options in automated mode.

COMMAND@LINE:~\$ solvate -s2

```

solvate <solute> { <solvent>} [<-options>]

<solute> = File with solute geometry (.com/log/inp/out/xyz/xtb)
<solvent> = File with solvent geometry (.com/log/inp/out/xyz/xtb)

-----
*STEP 2: Simulation [[MDRUN]] [-s2] «ORCA»«Gromacs»
-----
MDauto : Execute the MD simulation with automatic settings. [-ma] (●)(■)(*)
  » Description
    ORC: [Default: 50 ps/1.0 fs/001/ 250 solvent molecules]
    GMX: [Default: 1 ns/1.0 fs/001/2000 solvent molecules]
  + -----
»Automation Options:
  -auto : Start MD simulation with automatic settings. [-ra] (●)(■)(*)
  -init : Init. energy minimization with simulation box optimization procedure. [-ri] (●)(■)(*)
  -equi : Exec. MD equilibration procedure (with auto restart). [-re] (●)(■)(*)
  -prod : Exec. MD production procedure (with auto restart). [-rp] (●)(■)(*)
  -bomd : Run a BOMD simulation at GFN2-xTB level. [-rb] (●)(*)
»Procedure Options:
  -min : Execute an energy minimization of the simulation box. [-em] (●)(■)(*)
  -opt : Execute an optimization of the simulation box. [-bo] (●)(■)(*)
  -nvt : Run an equilibration simulation on NVT ensemble. [-nv] (●)(■)(*)
  -npt : Run an equilibration simulation on NPT ensemble. [-np] (■)(*)
  -prd : Run a production simulation on NVT/NPT ensemble. [-pd] (●)(■)(*)
»Settings Options:
  -met = MD simulation method (GFF|GF1|GF2). [Default: GFF] [Text] [-ms] (●)
  -prs = Pressure for the MD simul. (in bar). [Default: 1.0] [Real] [-ps] (■)
  -tcp = Time constant for pressure coupling (in ps). [Default: 0.50] [Real] [-tp] (■)
  -bar = Type of barostat pressure coupling. [Default: BRDS] [Text] [-br] (■)
    *BRDS = Berendsen | CRES = C-rescale | PARR = Parrinello| MTTK
  -tmp = Temperature for MD simulation (in K). [Default: 298.15] [Real] [-ts] (●)(■)
  -tct = Time constant for temperature coupling (in ps). [Default: 0.50] [Real] [-tc] (■)
  -ter = Type of thermostat temperature coupling. [Default: VRES] [Text] [-tr] (■)
    *BRDS = Berendsen | VRES = V-rescale | NOSE = Nose-Hoover| ADSN = Andersen
  -kap = Isothermal compressibility value (in bar-1). [Default: 4.5E-5] [Real] [-kp] (■)
  -tot = Simulation additional (ORCA) or total (GMX) time (in ps). [Default: Auto] [Real] [-tt] (●)(■)
  -nrs = Number of simulation run steps. [Default: Auto] [Int.] [-nr] (●)(■)
»Additional Options:
  -prc = Number of parallel process to be executed. [Default: 2] [-pc] (●)
  -deb : Verify generated files before submit. [Default: No] [-db] (●)(■)
-----
(*) Configurable options in automated mode. (●) ORCA available. (■) Gromacs available.

```

When accessing the options menu in stage 2, it is possible to notice the appearance of new symbols accompanying some options, like a square (■), a circle (●), and an asterisk (*). The square signifies that the option is available for the *GROMACS* program, while the circle is for the *ORCA* program. The asterisk indicates a customizable option when running in automatic mode.

COMMAND@LINE:~\$ solvate -s3

solvate <solute> { <solvent>} [<-options>]

<solute> = File with solute geometry (.com/log/inp/out/xyz/xtb)

<solvent> = File with solvent geometry (.com/log/inp/out/xyz/xtb)

*STEP 3: Analysis

[[DATAS+STATS+PLOTS+TRAJS]][-s3]

D_Tauto : Execute an automated properties extraction from simulation files. [-da] (●)(■)
 » Description
 Properties extraction + statistical and graphical analysis
 + -----
 -dat : Generate a dat file only. [-df] (●)(■)
 -cpt : Generate a dat file in compact format. [-cp] (●)(■)
 -dot : Convert dots to commas. [-dt] (●)(■)
 -res : Resume simulation data. [-re] (●)(■)
 -for : Force new properties extraction. [-fc] (●)(■)
 + -----
 -rms : RMSD analysis for SLT molecular residue. [-rd] (■)
 -rme : RMSD/E analysis for SLT molecular residue vs energy (extracted trajectory). [-ra] (■)
 -rdf : RDF analysis for center of masses of ref SLT and sel SVT residues. [-rd] (■)
 = [I:J] : RDF analysis for ref SLT/I and sel SVT/J labels. [-rd] (■)
 -pdf : PDF analysis for center of masses of ref SLT and sel SVT residues. [-pd] (●)(■)
 = [I:J] : PDF analysis for ref SLT/I and sel SVT/J indexes. [-pd] (●)(■)
 -cnv = Cumulative numerical value to be highlighted in the RDF analysis. [-cv] (■)
 + -----
 -plt : Generate graphs for params vs simulation time. [-pl] (●)(■)
 -stp : Plot graphs for params vs simulation step. [-st] (●)(■)
 + -----
 -trj : Analyze the trajectory file. [-tr] (●)(■)
 -ext : Extract a truncated trajectory file. [-tr] (●)(■)
 -ctr = [I:J] : Skip I equilibration steps and extract J production steps. [-ct] (●)(■)(*)
 -btr = [B:X] : Select frames from B trajectory blocks into X% final steps. [-bt] (●)(■)(*)
 -ptr = [P:D] : Select configurations around pressure P with tolerance ±D (in bar). [-pt] (■)(*)
 -prd : Select configuration production steps only and the corresponding properties. [-pr] (●)(■)(*)
 -grp : Extract short-ranged non-bonded potential energies. [-gr] (■)(*)
 -nbx : Do not make corrections for “fragmented” molecules near the box edges. [-nb] (■)
 -bak : Save intermediate PDB and XVG files for alternative conversions. [-bk] (■)
 -deb : Save intermediate XVG file and create a reconstructed ENT file. [-db] (■)

(*) Configurable options in automated mode. (●) ORCA available. (■) Gromacs available.

(†) RDF = Radial Distribution Function. (from TRJ.XTC file)

(‡) PDF = Pair Distribution Function. (from TRY.XYZ file)

COMMAND@LINE:~\$ solvate -s4

solvate <solute> { <solvent>} [<-options>]

<solute> = File with solute geometry (.com/log/inp/out/xyz/xtb)

<solvent> = File with solvent geometry (.com/log/inp/out/xyz/xtb)

*STEP 4: Clusterization

[[HBOND/MICRO]] [-s4]

Execute an automated H-bond detection and
 HBauto : characterization.

[-hb]

» Description

Nstr = 1 structure with maximal connections & minimal energy
 cTRJ = All production steps

+ -----

Nstr = Number of structures selected from simulation trajectory.	[Default: 1] [Int.]	[-ng] (*)
Nmax = Maximum number of attempts (for optimization procedure).	[Default: 10] [Int.]	[-na] (*)
dHbd = Maximum tolerated H-bond length (on trajectory structure).	[Default: 2.0] [Fix/Opt/Rel]	[-dh] (*)
cTRJ = N° of MD equilibration steps [:N° of MD production steps].	[Default: 0:0] [=Automatic]	[-ct] (*)
iRes : Include residuals H-bond interactions.	[Default: No]	[-ir] (*)
Prev : Execute only preliminary analysis.	[Default: No]	[-pr] (*)
Data : Preserve data about geometry optimization.	[Default: No]	[-dt] (*)
Chrg = Value of microsolvated solute charge.	[Default: 0] [Int.]	[-ch] (*)
Mult = Value of microsolvated solute multiplicity.	[Default: 1] [Int.]	[-ml] (*)
Solv Solvent to be used in ALPB solvation model.	[Default: WATER][Text]	[-sv] (*)

MSauto : Execute an automated microsolvation clusterization from simulation files.

[-ms]

» Description

bCon = 1 mol·kg⁻¹ (for setting the number of solvent molecules)
 Nstr = 1% of trajectory structures (1000 min, 10000 max)
 cTRJ = All production steps

+ -----

Nsol = Number of solvent molecules layers.	[Default: 1] [Int.]	[-nl] (*)
Nsvt = Number of solvent molecules in the clustering.	[Default: 0] [Int.]	[-ns] (*)
bCon = Molal conc. of the microsolvation cluster (in mol·kg ⁻¹).	[Default: 0.0] [Real]	[-bc] (*)
Nstr = Number of structures selected from simulation trajectory.	[Default: 1] [Int.]	[-ng] (*)
cTRJ = N° of MD equilibration steps [:N° of MD production steps].	[Default: 0:0] [=Automatic]	[-ct] (*)
Chrg = Value of microsolvated solute charge.	[Default: 0] [Int.]	[-ch] (*)
Mult = Value of microsolvated solute multiplicity.	[Default: 1] [Int.]	[-ml] (*)
Pres = Value of simulation pressure (in bar).	[Default: 1.0] [Real]	[-pr] (*)
Temp = Value of simulation temperature (in K).	[Default: 298] [Real]	[-tp] (*)
Solv Solvent to be used in ALPB solvation model.	[Default: WATER][Text]	[-sv] (*)
gRun : Execute gCalc analysis in automatic mode.	[Default: No] [Auto]	[-gc]

(*) Configurable options in automated mode.

COMMAND@LINE:~\$ solvate -s5

solvate <solute> { <solvent>} [<-options>]

<solute> = File with solute geometry (.com/log/inp/out/xyz/xtb)

<solvent> = File with solvent geometry (.com/log/inp/out/xyz/xtb)

*STEP 5: Optimization

[[GCALC]][-s5] «ORCA»«xTB»

● Step #1: Clusters Characterization

Characterization for structures selection in a defined energy window.

The characterizations are performed with xTB-GFF method.

This procedure generate the TRX files.

Automated execution: 25 kcal·mol⁻¹ energy window.

-ini : Execute clusters characterization and selection.

[Default: Auto]

[-ic]

● Step #2: Clusters Treatment

Optimizations after structures selection in a defined energy window.

The optimizations are performed with xTB-GFN2 method.

This procedure generate the TRY files.

Automated execution: 25 kcal·mol⁻¹ energy window.

-gfe = Gibbs free energy calculation method. (FCA|OPT|SAC|REL)

[Default: REL]

[-ge]

● Step #3: Energy Extrapolation

Gibbs free energy extrapolation of selected structures.

The extrapolation is executed at configured ONIOM method.

This procedure generate the TRZ files.

Automated execution: 10 kcal·mol⁻¹ energy window.

-ext = Energy extrapolation. (Gaussian|ORCA)(XTB|DFT)

[Default: ORCA/DFT]

[-ee]

● Additional Options

-win = Energy window for free energy calculation.

[Default: 10 kcal·mol⁻¹]

[-ew]

-max = Maximum number of structures into energy window.

[Default: Not defined]

[-nw] (*)

-rms = Maximal RMSD of structures into energy window.

[Default: Not defined]

[-rm] (*)

-chr = Value of microsolvated solute charge.

[Default: 0] [Int.]

[-ch] (*)

-mul = Value of microsolvated solute multiplicity.

[Default: 1] [Int.]

[-ml] (*)

-svt = Solvent type (for ALPB/PCM solvation method).

[Default: Auto]

[-sv] (*)

(*) Configurable options in automated mode. (†) For optimized structures only.

COMMAND@LINE:~\$ solvate -s6

solvate <*solute*> { <*solvent*>} [<*options*>]

<*solute*> = File with solute geometry (.com/log/inp/out/xyz/xtb)

<*solvent*> = File with solvent geometry (.com/log/inp/out/xyz/xtb)

*STEP 1: Packing [[PACKS+QMDF]] [-s1]

*STEP 2: Simulation [[MDRUN]] [-s2] «ORCA»«Gromacs»

*STEP 3: Analysis [[DATAS+STATS+PLOTS+TRAJS]] [-s3]

*STEP 4: Clusterization [[HBOND/MICRO]] [-s4]

*STEP 5: Optimization [[GCALC]] [-s5] «ORCA»«xTB»

*STEP 6: File Management [[FILES]] [-s6]

Flauto : Execute an automated file management. [-fa]

» Description

Compress if intermediate files are present

Extract if intermediate files are absent

+ -----

Compress : Compact the intermediate files. [Default: No] [Compact] [-cp]

Expand : Extract the intermediate files. [Default: No] [Extract] [-xp]

Application Examples

Integration with ORCA Program

Aqueous Systems: Example of Dimethylamine in Water (Two Oxidation States)

The computational study of redox reactions is an area that requires a precise description of the solvent effect. However, the use of implicit solvation methods has limitations regarding the size of the basis set that can be used due to the parameterization of the available PCM methods.^[1-2] An alternative approach is to model the solvated system of interest, explicitly including solvent molecules in a hybrid approach (microsolvation).^[3-4,5] However, to obtain an accurate description of the microsolvation of the system, especially when one intends to go beyond the inclusion of hydrogen bonds, it is necessary to perform a simulation in order to take into account the distribution of the solvent around the solute.

The initial configuration obtained is shown in Figure 1, an example of using the *SView* sub-module. By default, the *Solvate* output has a file format defined from the supplied inputs, unless specified by the user, but it can be converted to any other format from the *OutIn* sub-module. In the present example, the input and output files are of the same type, suitable for *ORCA* calculations. In any oxidation state, the simulation box can be inserted in an implicit description of the solvent to reduce border effects and represent long-range effects.

Figure 1: Example of using *SView*, interface module for structural visualization programs (such as *JMol* and *VMD*, selected according to the information available in the input file). In this example an initial simulation box is shown with a dimethylamine molecule visualized in *VDW* mode in the center of a sphere with 250 water molecules visualized in the *DynamicBonds* with *QuickSurf* mode of the *VMD* program. The same box can be viewed in different modes, all activated directly from the command line.

Chart 1: Initial and final configurations of the oxidized and neutral states of dimethylamine in water; highlighting the solute in the center, and the counterion at the edge of the simulation box.

Chart 2: Temperature and energy versus simulation time for cationic and neutral states. The red line corresponds to the stochastic average.

Cation (Reference State)

Neutral (Reduced State)

Non-Aqueous Systems: Example of Methanesulfonic Acid in DMSO (Two Protonation States)

The acidity of a compound in solution, described by its pK_a value, plays a key role in many fields of chemistry, including biochemistry, pharmacology, and environmental chemistry.^[6] Thus, predicting pK_a values is of great importance in practical applications. However, an accurate prediction through computational methods faces significant challenges, similar to the calculation of reduction potentials, mainly due to the solvent effect.^[7-8]

To investigate the pK_a of the methanesulfonic acid in DMSO from its neutral to deprotonated state, aiming for the explicit inclusion of only hydrogen bonds, a simulation can be performed with *ORCA* program, at the AIMD/xTB-GFF level. In this example, a spherical box containing one molecule of the acid in its center and 75 molecules of DMSO was prepared (in this case, with the same total number of atoms in the solvent from the previous example with water). For the deprotonated state of methanesulfonic acid, one solvent molecule was replaced by one protonated DMSO as a counter-ion. As in the previous example, the simulation was prepared with the box immersed in an implicit solvent. The initial configuration and the corresponding simulation can be obtained by running *Solvate* with the same sequence of commands described previously. A brief summary of obtained properties in this simulation is shown below.

Chart 3: Initial and final configurations of protonated and deprotonated states of methanesulfonic acid in water, highlighting the solute in the center, and the counterion at the edge of the simulation box.

Chart 4: Temperature and energy versus simulation time for protonated and deprotonated states of methanesulfonic acid. The red line corresponds to the stochastic average.

Basic (Reference State)

Acid (Protonated State)

Table 1: Statistical parameters for the two protonation states of methanesulfonic in DMSO from an ORCA simulation.

Time : 40 ps Count : 40 K frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Acid			
Temperature (K)	298.1405	0.0198	3.9644
Potential (ua)	-102.6925	0.0001	0.0275
Basic			
Temperature (K)	298.1450	0.0197	3.9304
Potential (ua)	-102.6754	0.0001	0.0268

Integration with GROMACS Program

Aqueous Systems

- *Example of Dimethylamine in Water*

Chart 5: Initial and final configurations of the neutral state of dimethylamine in water, highlighting the solute in the center of the simulation box.

Chart 6: Properties versus simulation time for the neutral state of dimethylamine in water. The red line corresponds to the stochastic average.

A summary of the results obtained for the simulation production stage of the dimethylamine in water is presented below.

Table 2: Statistical parameters for the neutral state of ethanol in water obtained from the entire production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 5 ns Count : 2.5 M frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.2753	0.3293	520.6952
Temperature (K)	298.1494	0.0024	3.8242
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	0.9987	0.0000	0.0057
Short-Range (ua)	-87.7655	0.0085	13.4568
Potential (ua)	-35.6652	0.0001	0.1158
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	4.7530		

The DATAS module has features for filtering properties and trajectory configurations based on different criteria. For example, the properties extraction considering a target pressure of 1.0 bar, in a window of ± 0.4 bar, by executing the following command:

```
solvate solute.gro water.gro -nm 2000 -datas -ptrj [1.0:0.4]
```

resulted in the set of statistical data presented below.

Table 3: Statistical parameters for the neutral state of ethanol in water obtained from the extracted production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 5 ns Count : 2231 frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.0020	0.0050	0.2339
Temperature (K)	298.0718	0.0783	3.6969
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	0.9985	0.0001	0.0052
Short-Range (ua)	-87.2229	0.2874	13.5759
Potential (ua)	-35.6646	0.0024	0.1134
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	3.9100		

Pressure

Temperature

Density

Short-Range

Potential Energy

Radial Distribution Function

Other important analyses carried out via the DATAS module are the RMSD analysis of the solute (useful in identifying conformational changes throughout the simulation) and RDF. For example, the analysis of the RDF (together with the cumulative count result) between the N1 reference atom of dimethylamine and the OW oxygen atom of water is performed from the command:

```
solvate solute.gro water.gro -nm 2000 -datas -rdf [N1:OW]
```

The RDF diagrams obtained for dimethylamine in water are shown below.

■ **Example of Ethanol in Water**

Chart 7: Initial and final configurations of the neutral state of ethanol in water, highlighting the solute in the center of the simulation box.

Chart 8: Properties versus simulation time for the neutral state of ethanol in water. The red line corresponds to the stochastic average.

Table 4: Statistical parameters for the neutral state of ethanol in water obtained from the entire production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 5 ns Count : 2.5 M frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.2753	0.3293	520.6952
Temperature (K)	298.1494	0.0024	3.8242
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	0.9987	0.0000	0.0057
Short-Range (ua)	-87.7655	0.0085	13.4568
Potential (ua)	-35.6652	0.0001	0.1158
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	4.7530		

Table 5: Statistical parameters for the neutral state of ethanol in water obtained from the extracted production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 5 ns Count : 2231 frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.0020	0.0050	0.2339
Temperature (K)	298.0718	0.0783	3.6969
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	0.9985	0.0001	0.0052
Short-Range (ua)	-87.2229	0.2874	13.5759
Potential (ua)	-35.6646	0.0024	0.1134
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	3.9100		

Pressure

Temperature

Density

Short-Range

Potential Energy

■ **Example of 1,4-Dioxane in Water**

Chart 9: Initial and final configurations of the neutral state of dioxane in water, highlighting the solute in the center of the simulation box.

Chart 10: Properties versus simulation time for the neutral state of dioxane in water. The red line corresponds to the stochastic average.

Table 6: Statistical parameters for the neutral state of dioxane in water obtained from the entire production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 5 ns Count : 2.5 M frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.2679	0.3282	518.9048
Temperature (K)	298.0277	0.0024	3.8574
Density ($\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$)	0.9989	0.0000	0.0057
Short-Range (ua)	-109.2713	0.0093	14.7108
Potential (ua)	-35.6801	0.0001	0.1154
κ_T (10^{-5} bar^{-1})	4.7940		

Table 7: Statistical parameters for the neutral state of dioxane in water obtained from the extracted production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 5 ns Count : 2302 frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.0126	0.0048	0.2299
Temperature (K)	298.0523	0.0809	3.8831
Density ($\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$)	0.9988	0.0001	0.0052
Short-Range (ua)	-109.1596	0.3005	14.4182
Potential (ua)	-35.6817	0.0024	0.1144
κ_T (10^{-5} bar^{-1})	3.9950		

Pressure

Temperature

Density

Short-Range

Potential Energy

Non-Aqueous Systems

Solvate has facilities for preparing and submitting simulations in solvents other than water. The entire procedure follows the same set of commands. Some examples (ethanol and dioxane in DMSO) are summarized below.

■ Example of Ethanol in DMSO

Chart 11: Initial and final configurations of the neutral state of ethanol in DMSO, highlighting the solute in the center of the simulation box.

Chart 12: Properties versus simulation time for the neutral state of ethanol in DMSO. The red line corresponds to the stochastic average.

Table 8: Statistical parameters for the neutral state of ethanol in DMSO obtained from the entire production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 4 ns Count : 2.0 M frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.0439	0.1872	264.7776
Temperature (K)	298.1504	0.0014	1.9122
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	1.1255	0.0000	0.0030
Short-Range (ua)	-89.2583	0.0056	7.9044
Potential (ua)	-103.8646	0.0001	0.1811
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	3.9400		

Table 9: Statistical parameters for the neutral state of ethanol in DMSO obtained from the extracted production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 4 ns Count : 2302 frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.0023	0.0046	0.2302
Temperature (K)	298.2133	0.0381	1.8888
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	1.1256	0.0001	0.0029
Short-Range (ua)	-89.4004	0.1568	7.7809
Potential (ua)	-103.8598	0.0036	0.1808
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	3.6210		

Pressure

Temperature

Density

Short-Range

Potential Energy

Root Mean Square Deviation

The analysis of the RMSD analysis of the *solute* fragment is performed from the command:

```
solvate solute.gro water.gro -nm 2000 -datas -rmsd
```

The RMSD diagrams obtained for dimethylamine in water are shown below.

■ **Example of 1,4-Dioxane in DMSO**

Chart 13: Initial and final configurations of the neutral state of dioxane in DMSO, highlighting the solute in the center of the simulation box.

Chart 14: Properties versus simulation time for the neutral state of dioxane in DMSO. The red line corresponds to the stochastic average.

Table 10: Statistical parameters for the neutral state of dioxane in DMSO obtained from the entire production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 4.7 ns Count : 2.4 M frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.0644	0.1720	264.5452
Temperature (K)	298.1550	0.0012	1.9057
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	1.1256	0.0000	0.0029
Short-Range (ua)	-97.6808	0.0060	9.2665
Potential (ua)	-103.8669	0.0001	0.1791
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	3.8290		

Table 11: Statistical parameters for the neutral state of dioxane in DMSO obtained from the extracted production stage of a GROMACS simulation.

Time : 4.7 ns Count : 2856 frames	Average Value	Standard Error	Standard Deviation
Pressure (bar)	1.0010	0.0044	0.2330
Temperature (K)	298.1907	0.0354	1.8901
Density (g·cm ⁻³)	1.1256	0.0001	0.0027
Short-Range (ua)	-97.9901	0.1773	9.4726
Potential (ua)	-103.8680	0.0034	0.1797
κ_T (10 ⁻⁵ bar ⁻¹)	3.2930		

Pressure

Temperature

Density

Short-Range

Potential Energy

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